
A novel denoising method using connectivity judgment and adaptive filtering

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Abstract - The noise caused by various external factors gives a negative effect on optical measurements, object detection, etc. The filter-based random impulse denoising methods have the disadvantage of poor noise detection accuracy when the noise density is high and poor noise removal for weak intensity noises. In this paper, a novel denoising method using connectivity judgment and adaptive filter is proposed. First, the background noise and edge noise are separated individually by the connectivity judgment based on the brightness different of the pixels. And, the filter size is actively adapted according to the magnitude of the local noise density, and reasonable filter weight is determined. Then, high density background noise is removed by using the recursive method and edge noise is removed by using the edge direction information. Experiments were performed with image data which is added random impulse noise between 0-255 and Gaussian noise with 0 mean and variance of 20 at the ranging from 10 to 50%, and the proposed method was superior in terms of noise detection accuracy, speed and noise reduction accuracy compared to the previous methods.

Key Words: connectivity, noise detection, adaptive filtering, noise removal, PSNR

1.INTRODUCTION

During the machining of spark discharge mode, fine metal particles and oil droplets separated from the tool and material are mixed together and scattered in the atmosphere by the tool rotating at high speed, resulting in dust cloud formation. Such dust clouds are not well observed at normal vision, but the noise of low intensity and uncertain type, and random impulse noises of high intensity are seen to be in a disordered state by mixing in the images obtained with $1\mu m$ resolution cameras. In this case, the result of the detailed characteristics analysis of the these noise reveals that petroleum dust has a strength between 5 and 20, and the distribution characteristics in each observation image are not fixed, accounting for 80% of the total noise. Also, the metal particles are represented by random impulse noise with intensities above 50, accounting for 20% of the total noise. In general, in the case of a sharp-contrast image, the noise of less intensity than 10 is often neglected or removed through Gaussian smoothing, which does not significantly affect the performance of the precision measurement. However, if there are not less portions with not clear contrast in the boundary of the

precision measurement object, the small intensity noise in these parts will have a great negative effect on detecting the correct boundary and, finally, will be an important factor in further deterioration of the quality of image analysis. Reflecting this realistic requirement, many studies on noise reduction while retaining the visual features such as boundaries, colors, and textures are in progress. Researchers have used Wiener adaptive filters and median filters to remove the Gaussian noise and impulsive noise that are widely present in reality, and many random impulse denoising methods based on median filtering have been investigated[2-6]. How well the noise is removed is determined by the number of denoised pixels and the number of correctly recovered pixels in practice. It also depends on the number of pixels whose intensity is changed because it is misjudged as noise. Generally, there are peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), mean square error (MSE), and structural similarity index (SSIM) in the performance evaluation of denoising methods [1].

In reality, there are many Gaussian noises with zero mean and v^2 variance. Wiener adaptive filters are widely used to remove these Gaussian noises. When $a(x, y)$ is the original image, $\mu(x, y)$, $\sigma^2(x, y)$ are the local mean and the local variance of the original image, the resulting image $b(x, y)$ is as follows.

$$b(x, y) = \mu(x, y) + \frac{\max\{\sigma^2(x, y) - v^2, 0\}}{\max\{\sigma^2(x, y), v^2\}} (a(x, y) - \mu(x, y)) \quad (1)$$

If the variance of the noise is unknown, the mean value of the local variances in each pixel is used as the variance of the noise. This filter has the disadvantage of blurring the boundary.

A vector median filter (VMF), one of the most used nonlinear filters for impulse noise removal, modifies all pixels through vector median value processing. This applies to both noisy and non-noisy pixels, thus removing some important detail information and thus blurring the image. Hence, this filter is developed into central weighted vector median filters (CWVMF) [2] and switching-based vector median filters (SVMF) [3], but the performance of these filters has the disadvantage of being significantly degraded as noise intensity increases. In [4], an AVMF+WMF method is proposed to remove impulse noise using a weighted median filter after noise detection with an adaptive vector median filter. In [5], a SVM+AF method is proposed to classify noise types and density characteristics based on machine learning and to apply adaptive filters based on them. In [6], a RAFF method called region adaptive feature filtering is proposed. When $W_{V \times V}^{(i, j)}$ is a neighborhood

window of size $V \times V$ over the center pixel $C(i, j)$, rearrange the 1-D array of size $V \times V$ from the absolute difference between the central pixel in the window and its neighboring pixels in order of magnitude, and calculate the average value MMV of the first N values of this array. Then, MMV is compared with the appropriate threshold T and judged as a noisy pixel if $MMV > T$. Then, to improve the detection efficiency at all noise levels, different parameters are used, they set parameters as $(V, N, T) = \{(3, 5, 16), (5, 11, 22)\}$ [6]. After noise detection in the same way as above, the size of filtering window applied to noise reduction is changed to 13×13 depending on the noise density. Then, the filter weight used is as follows.

$$wn(x, y, i, j) = \frac{\varepsilon(i, j, x, y) \cdot \overline{DM(i+x, j+y)}}{\sum_{p=-k}^{p=k} \sum_{q=-k}^{q=k} \varepsilon(i, j, x, y) \cdot \overline{DM(i+p, j+q)}} \quad (2)$$

Here $DM(x, y)$ is the value of 0 if the pixel in (x, y) is noisy, 1 if not, and $\varepsilon(i, j, x, y)$ is the reciprocal of absolute difference between the mean value of the non-noisy pixels in the (i, j) neighborhood and the pixel value of the $(i+x, j+y)$ position. This method shows a higher performance in noise detection and noise reduction compared to the previous works, but has the disadvantage of oversized filter windows at high noise densities and biased filter weights to the average of non-noisy pixels. Also, the minimum mean value method used for noise detection has the drawback of slow detection speed, low detection accuracy at high noise density or near the step boundary. The ROAD-TGM-HT[1] method, which combines the Rank-Ordered Absolute Differences with Trimmed Global Mean Filter with Hough transform, is proposed. The ROAD-TGM-HT method removes noise in two steps. First, they choose the size of the neighborhood window used for denoising as 5×5 and rearrange the 1-D array of 5×5 size from the absolute difference between the central pixel and its neighborhood pixels in order of magnitude. And the sum of the first 12 values of this array is selected, and the ROAD for the current pixel is determined as follows.

$$ROAD_m(x) = \sum_{i=1}^m r_i(x) \quad (3)$$

In the above equation m is 12 and $r_i(x)$ is the i -th value of the rearranged absolute difference values. If the ROAD value of the current pixel is greater than a certain threshold, it is judged as a noisy pixel, and if it is smaller, it is not a noisy pixel. If this threshold is large, many noisy pixels are judged as non-noisy pixels, while if they are small, non-noisy pixels may be misjudged as noisy pixels. In [1], this value is set to 40, and it is reported that the filter depends on the characteristics of the image applied and on the noise intensity. Then, the noise reduction was performed by combining the TGM with HT [7]. However, this method also has a drawback of slow noise detection because when detecting noise, it computes the absolute difference between 25 pixels in the neighborhood for each pixel, and then rearranges in order of magnitude and adds the first 12 values. Furthermore, the Hough transform is used to find a straight line with non-noisy pixels and the noisy pixels on line are replaced by the average of non-noisy pixels, so denoising speed becomes slow.

Most of the noise reduction techniques proposed earlier have denoised by assuming that the image is corrupted by a single type of noise [8]. However, in reality, images can be

corrupted by more than one noise at a time. Then, individual denoising techniques cannot effectively eliminate the mixed noises. Recently, several filters have been proposed to remove mixed noises. To eliminate the mixed noise, at least two filters must be made to estimate the noise of a particular type. In [9-10], fuzzy rules are used to realize weighted averaging, where the similarity weights and noise weights between the pixels under consideration and neighbors are calculated. However, this method cannot achieve good performance when the noise intensity in local regions is high.

In addition, bilateral filters (BF) [12, 13], triangular filters (TF) [14, 15] and switching Bilateral filters (SBF) [16, 17] have been proposed. It is evaluated that this method is well adapted to Gaussian noise. The TF method is used to perform noise removal on pixels corrupted by impulsive noise using a new parameter, the impulse weight function, based on the hybrid scheme. However, the TF filter cannot effectively distinguish the noise type when the noise intensity is high. Moreover, this method does not handle noise like salt-pepper and speckle noise well. In addition, SBF is proposed to remove both noise including Gaussian noise and salt-pepper noise. This method determines the noise type using the classified 1/4 partition median vector (SQMV) and the reference median (RM) [18]. Then, based on the detected noise type, the previously determined filter parameters, spatial weight σ_S and differential weight σ_R are interchangeably used to remove noise [19].

In addition, there are adaptive median filters (AMF)[22], decision-based algorithms (DBA)[23], noise adaptive fuzzy switching median filters (NAFSMF)[24], adaptive weighted median filters (AWMF)[25], differential adaptive median filters (DAMF)[26], Modified Decision Based Unsymmetrical Trimmed Median Filter (MDBUTMF)[27], and Rank-Ordered Absolute Differences with Trimmed Global Mean Filter (ROAD-TGM)[28,29].

The organization of this paper is as follows. The noise detection mechanism is formulated in Section II. Section III describes the proposed filtering technique. Section IV presents experimental results and Section V concludes the paper.

2. NOISE DETECTION MECHANISM

The noise has a certain brightness value difference with its neighboring pixels, and as the result, the noise is isolated from the neighboring pixels that are not noise. In addition, a non-noisy background (boundary) pixel is interconnected with all pixels of background (boundary) pixel set with include itself, with respect to the brightness difference criterion with neighboring pixels, and then by judging the number of elements in the connected pixel sets, pixel can be estimated to be noise if the number of elements is less than a certain threshold.

To separate the image into groups of pixels connected according to the brightness difference criterion with neighboring pixels, we judge that two pixels belong to the same set of connected pixels together if there exists a pixel

sequence $\{r_i | i = \overline{1, k}\}$ that satisfies the following condition for two pixels $p(s, t)$ and $q(u, v)$ of image I .

- ① $r_i \in I, i = \overline{1, k}$
- ② $r_1 = p, r_k = q$
- ③ $(r_{i+1} \in N_{3 \times 3}(r_i) \wedge |I(r_i) - I(r_{i+1})| < th1) \vee$
 $(r_{i+1} \in N_{5 \times 5}(r_i) \setminus N_{3 \times 3}(r_i) \wedge |I(r_i) - I(r_{i+1})| < th2)$
- ④ $p \in N_{3 \times 3}(q) \Rightarrow |I(p) - I(q)| < th1$

Where $I(p)$ is the brightness value at pixel p , $N_{3 \times 3}(r_i)$, $N_{5 \times 5}(r_i)$ represents the $3 \times 3, 5 \times 5$ neighborhood of pixel r_i , and $th1, th2$ is the threshold that determines the connectivity between two pixels. The reason why connectivity is judged using two neighbors is that, in the case of high noise density, a possibility that all pixels in the 3×3 neighborhood will be noise may exists. In this case, even if a given pixel is not noisy, since all the pixels in the neighborhood are noisy, this pixel is isolated and therefore it can be judged as noise. However, when connectivity is judged to pixels of 5×5 neighborhood, if non-noisy pixels connected to a given pixel are present in the 5×5 neighborhood, then these pixels are connected to each other, which is judged to be non-noisy, leading to higher accuracy of noise detection. It is because there is little possibility that all pixels in 5×5 neighborhood are noisy. We use the following algorithm to separate image I into connected pixel sets according to the connectivity criterion.

INPUT: $M \times N$ Images I , $th1, th2$

OUTPUT: connected pixel sets $\{\Omega_i | i = \overline{1, L}\}$

Initializing: $L = 0, A_{M \times N} = 0_{M \times N}$ (Zero Matrix)

Step 1. *for* $i = 0, i < M, i++$

Step 2. *for* $j = 0, j < N, j++$

Step 3. If $a_{i,j} > 0$ then Step 2.

Step 4. $a_{i,j} = 1, \Omega_L = \{(i, j)\}, B = \Omega_L, L = L + 1$

Step 5. $B' = \emptyset, C = \emptyset$

Step 6. *for* $k = 0, k < |B|, k++$

Step 7. Construct 5×5 neighborhood pixel set $N_{5 \times 5}(b_k)$ of $b_k \in B$

Step 8. *for* $s = 0, s < |N_{5 \times 5}(b_k)|, s++$

Step 8-1. If $A(c_s) \neq 0 (c_s \in N_{5 \times 5}(b_k))$ then Step 8.

Step 8-2. If $\|b_k - c_s\| < 2$ and $|I(b_k) - I(c_s)| \geq th1$ then

$A(c_s) = -1, C = C \cup \{c_s\}$ Step 8.

Step 8-3. If $\|b_k - c_s\| \geq 2$ and $|I(b_k) - I(c_s)| \geq th2$ then Step 8.

Step 8-4. $\Omega_L = \Omega_L \cup \{c_s\}, B' = B' \cup \{c_s\}, A(c_s) = 1$, Step 8.

Step 9. $B' \neq \emptyset$ then $B = B'$, Step 5.

Step 10. $B' = \emptyset$ then $A(c_s) = 0$ for all $c_s \in C$, Step 2.

Step 11. End

Fig 1. a) noise image, b) background noise map, c) residual noise map, d) boundary noise map, e) misjudged noise map

Through the above algorithm, if the count of pixels in a set of separated pixels is large, the pixel set can be defined as a background pixel set, if the count of pixels is small, as a noise set, and if the count of pixels is small or medium, as a boundary pixel set. The cardinal number of boundary pixel set is lower than the background pixel set, there are many similar boundary pixel set to the noise set, so there is a great possibility of misjudging as a noise set. It is generally associated with the fact that the brightness values of boundary pixels are not uniform compared to the background and are much less connected due to noise.

The noise set is classified into a set of background noise, a set of boundary noise, and a set of pixels misjudged as noise. Here, the background noise represents the noise witch present in the background of the image, and the boundary noise represents the noise witch present in the neighborhood of the boundary. The background noise set is a set of noises witch present in the background, so the neighboring pixels of the noise set are mostly composed of points of the background pixel set surrounding the noise set, and the rest is composed of the pixels of other noise sets. Thus, the background noise can be determined by judging the count of pixels in the connected pixel set and the maximum count of adjacent points among the set of background pixel adjacent to this set. It is possible that the noise density is high and, so if there are many noises in the neighborhood of the noise set, it is judged not to be background noise set. Fig. 1b shows the position of the background noise in low noise density, and c shows the position of the residual noise except background noise in the pixel set judged as noise.

The boundary noise set is a set of noises that lie near the boundary, and count of pixels of the set is very small, and is adjacent to the background pixel set, boundary neighborhood pixel set, noise set. The boundary noise set has a characteristic witch the count of pixels is smaller compared to the nearby pixel set, but the boundary noise set and the small size of the background noise set at high noise density are difficult to distinguish. Thus, there will be some misjudged noise set as boundary noise in the background region, as shown in Fig. 1c. However, as shown in Fig. 1c, the boundary noise set is adjacent to the boundary neighborhood pixel set misjudged as noise, so has the characteristic of consisting of a thick line containing the boundary, but the background noise set is isolated. Using these characteristic, the background and boundary noise set can be detected accurately by separating each other. The following algorithm shows the process of detecting background and boundary noise set from connected pixel sets.

INPUT: connected pixel sets $\{\Omega_i | i = \overline{1, L}\}$, noise judgement threshold $T1, T2$

OUTPUT: background noise map DMB , boundary noise map DME

Initializing: $DMB_{M \times N} = DME_{M \times N} = 0_{M \times N}$ (zero matrix), $DMT_{M \times N} = 0_{M \times N}, i = 0$

Step 1. If $|\Omega_i| > T1$ then step 5.

Step 2. Calculate $n = \max_{0 \leq j < L, j \neq i} |\partial(I \setminus \Omega_i) \cap \Omega_j|$, $k = \text{argmax}_{0 \leq j < L, j \neq i} |\partial(I \setminus \Omega_i) \cap \Omega_j|$.

Step 3. If $n > |\partial(I \setminus \Omega_i)|/2$ and $n > |\Omega_i|$ and $|\Omega_k| > T1$ then

$$DMB(a_t) = 1 \left(t = \overline{|\Omega_i|}, a_t \in \Omega_i \right).$$

$$\text{else } DMT(a_t) = 1 \left(t = \overline{|\Omega_i|}, a_t \in \Omega_i \right).$$

Step 4. $i++$, if $i < L$ then step 1, else step 5.

Step 5. $for i = 0, i < M, i++$

Step 6. $for j = 0, j < N, j++$

Step 7. if $DMT(i, j) == 0$ then step 6.

Step 8. If the count of pixels of 1 in the 3×3 neighborhood of (i, j) in DMT is less than $T2$, then $DMB(i, j) = 1$,

Else if the count of pixels in a connected pixel set containing (i, j) is less than $T1$, then $DME(i, j) = 1$

Step 9. end.

We determined the threshold for connectivity judgment as $th1 = 5$, $th2 = 5$, and the threshold used for noise detection as $T1 = 20$, $T2 = 4$. The reason is that, in general, if the brightness difference between two adjacent pixels is less than 5, the two pixels are not significantly different visually and appear to be almost the same pixel. And the thresholds used for noise detection were determined based on the analysis of the noise detection results obtained according to the thresholds after adding random impulse noise to different images of the BSDS[20] database with known contour information. Proposed method is a global connectivity judgment method, so even if the brightness difference between pixels within a local region is above a threshold, these pixels are all merged into a single connected set by judging for connected pixels in the global range. As a result, even if a background pixel set with some brightness differences is present, it is correctly classified as a background pixel set by connectivity judgment, and indeed only isolated noise is correctly detected. The total noise map is.

$$DM(i, j) = \begin{cases} 1, & DMB(i, j) = 1 \vee DME(i, j) = 1 \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

3. PROPOSED FILTERING TECHNIQUE

For noise reduction, we first consider how to actively set the filter window size based on the local noise density. The adaptive window size $W_{2k+1} \times W_{2k+1}$ for noise filtering in the detected noise pixel $I(i, j)$ is determined by using a recursive method as follows

INPUT: position of noise pixel (i, j) , noise map DM

OUTPUT: adaptive window size W_{kf}

Step 1. Initialize $k = 1, k_{max}$.

Step 2. Calculate the number of noise in the window.

$$S = \sum_{x=-k}^k \sum_{y=-k}^k DM(i+x, j+y) \quad (5)$$

Step 3. Repeat the following condition until $k \leq k_{max}$

if $k < k_{max}$ and $S > \frac{(2k+1) \times (2k+1)}{2}$ then $k = k + 1$, Recalculate S_z with Eq. (12) and go to Step 3.

if $k < k_{max}$ and $S \leq \frac{(2k+1) \times (2k+1)}{2}$ then, Fix k and set the final window size to $W_{kf} = 2k + 1$.

if $k = k_{max}$ then $W_{kf} = 2k_{max}$.

Why the parameter value for determining the maximum window size is determined by k_{max} in the algorithm is generally due to the fact that large filter window size leads to a decrease in the filtering speed and blurring of the filtering results, and if the filter window size is too small, cannot achieve good filtering results when noise density is high. The above method of determining the adaptive window size allows a higher noise filtering speed than using a fixed window. Since the maximum filter window size proposed in RAFF [6] is 13×13 , it has the disadvantage that the boundary part can be blurred by the filter and the processing speed is also slow.

A. background noise removal

The method of background noise reduction is as follows.

INPUT: image I , noise pixel position (i, j) , noise map DM

OUTPUT: noise-filtered pixel $F(i, j)$

Step 1. Determine the adaptive window size k using a noise map.

Step 2. If the count of noise in the adaptive window S is $S > (2k + 1) \times (2k + 1)/2$, then filtering is as follows.

First, we compute the average $\lambda(i, j)$ of the non-noisy pixels in the adaptive window.

$$\lambda(i, j) = \frac{\sum_{x=-k}^k \sum_{y=-k}^k \{DM(i+x, j+y) \cdot I(i+x, j+y)\}}{\sum_{x=-k}^k \sum_{y=-k}^k DM(i+x, j+y)} \quad (6)$$

Here $\overline{DM(i, j)} = 1 - DM(i, j)$.

Then, the difference between $\lambda(i, j)$ and surrounding pixels is calculated and the filter weight is determined by the double-sided filter format as follows.

$$\varepsilon(x, y, i, j) = |\lambda(i, j) - I(i+x, j+y)| \quad (7)$$

$$wg(x, y, i, j) = \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{x^2+y^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)}{2\pi\sigma^2} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{\varepsilon(x, y, i, j) - \varepsilon_{min}}} \quad (8)$$

$$\varepsilon \begin{matrix} \min \\ -k \leq x \leq k \\ -k \leq y \leq k \end{matrix} \quad (9)$$

In the above equation, σ is set to $\sigma = \frac{2k+1}{3}$ so that the two-dimensional normal distribution within the filter

window lies more than 90% using the 3σ -law of probability. In RAFF [6], the filter weight is set to $(\varepsilon(x, y, i, j) + 1)^{-1}$. However, this weight did not reflect the distance relationship between the noisy pixel and the nearby non-noisy pixels. In particular, weight value is taken based on the minimum value of brightness difference between the mean value of the non-noisy pixels in the noisy pixel neighborhood and non-noisy individual pixels. As a result, when this minimum is 1, the weight ratio applied to a pixel with a brightness difference of 1 and a pixel with a brightness difference of 10 is 10:1, and the effect of the two pixels on the filter value determination is 10 times different. However, if this minimum is 10, the weight ratio applied to pixels with a brightness difference of 10 and 20 is 2:1, which is quite comparable to the above case. However, in the above two cases, the difference in brightness between the two pixels is 10, which is not significantly different visually. As a result, it is not right to apply opposite weights as in the above two cases, depending on the minimum brightness difference, nor is it right to apply weights at a ratio of 10:1 for the minimum brightness difference of 1. Therefore, we reflected the distance relation between the pixel participating in the filtering and center pixel to the weight, and defined the inverse of the root of the value brightness difference minus the minimum brightness difference as the base weight. The reason for subtracting the minimum brightness difference from the brightness difference is to normalize the weight of the range kernel function. The reason for applying the root is to maintain the proportionality between the weight of the range kernel function and the weight of the spatial kernel function, using the characteristic that the difference between the mean of the non-noisy background pixels in the filter and the background pixel is typically not more than 10. For a filter window size of 3×3 , the ratio between the maximum and minimum values of the spatial kernel and range kernel functions is 0.15:1 and 0.05:0.3, so the ratio of 1:6 is maintained.

Then, the filter weights calculated as above are normalized.

$$wgn(x, y, i, j) = \frac{wg(x, y, i, j) \cdot \overline{DM(i+x, j+y)}}{\sum_{p=-k}^k \sum_{q=-k}^k wg(p, q, i, j) \cdot \overline{DM(i+p, j+q)}} \quad (10)$$

Finally, we perform the filtering as follows.

$$F(i, j) = \sum_{x=-k}^k \sum_{y=-k}^k \{wgn(x, y, i, j) \cdot I(i+x, j+y)\} \quad (11)$$

If we use the above algorithm, the filtering process is not performed if the count of noisy pixels in the adaptive window region of the noisy pixel is larger than $(2k+1) \times (2k+1)/2$. Thus, we cannot remove all the noise with a single filtering process, but the noise density decreases through the filtering process. If we iteratively use the above algorithm, we can gradually remove all the noise, with the noise density decreasing continuously. The SVM+AF and RAFF used median filtering for high noise density, but the filtering results are not accurate because the pixels judged as noise are used for median filtering. Also, in RAFF [6], the filter window size is extended to 13×13 for high noise densities until the noise density in the window is reduced. In this case, because of the excessive window size, the filtering result for a given pixel will lose local features,

resulting in blurring of the image and slowing the filtering speed. However, in the case of recursive methods, more accurate noise reduction results can be obtained by removing the noise in the part of low noise density of its neighborhood in turn for the noise in the region of high noise density, as a result, dropping down the noise density gradually, so finally performing noise filtering in the context of the resulting low noise density. Also, the total count of noise points is fixed and the window size used for filtering is smaller than that of the previous literature, so the noise reduction speed is higher than that of the previous literature.

B. boundary noise removal

The method of eliminating boundary noise is as follows.

INPUT: image I , noise pixel position (i, j) , noise map DM

OUTPUT: noise-filtered pixel $F(i, j)$

Step 1. The adaptive window size is determined using the boundary noise map.

Step 2. If the count of noise in the adaptive window S is $S > (2k+1) \times (2k+1) \times 2/3$, then median filtering is performed, else, we perform the filtering as follows.

Using [21], we obtain the AMDD of K directions and hence determine the boundary direction as follows.

$$\theta = \underset{\theta_i = i\pi/K, i=0, K-1}{\operatorname{argmax}} \{AMDD(\mathbf{n}|I, \sigma, \rho, i)\} \quad (12)$$

Then, the filter weight is obtained as.

$$wg(x, y, \theta) = w(x \cos \theta - y \sin \theta, x \sin \theta + y \cos \theta) \quad (13)$$

$$w(x, y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_x \sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_y} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{x^2}{2\sigma_x^2} + \frac{y^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right)\right) \quad (14)$$

Then, the filter weights are normalized using (10) and then filtering is done using (11). We determined as $K = 4$, $\sigma = 1.5$, $\rho = 2.5$, $\sigma_x = 1$, $\sigma_y = 2.5$ through experiments using the BSDS [20] database.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We selected 50 images of 256×256 size of micro-hole of the $150 \mu\text{m}$ diameter taken by $1 \mu\text{m}$ resolution camera as experimental data. The performance is measured in terms of peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR) [30]. PSNR value, used similarly in [31], is defined as

$$PSNR(I', I) = 10 \log_{10} \frac{I_{max}^2}{MSE(I', I)} \quad (15)$$

$$MSE(I', I) = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N (I(i, j) - I'(i, j))^2 \quad (16)$$

Here I', I represents the reconstructed image and $M \times N$ is the image size, and I_{max} represents the maximum intensity value. We also selected the noise detection rate and the noise detection speed as performance evaluation indices. If N_{real} is the actual count of noise pixels, $N_{correct}$ is the count of correctly detected noise pixels, and N_{error} is the

count of falsely detected noise pixels, then noise detection rate is determined as follows.

$$DR = \frac{\left(\frac{N_{correct}}{N_{real}} + \left(1 - \frac{N_{error}}{(M \times N - N_{real})} \right) \right)}{2} \quad (17)$$

The computer used in the experiments is core i5-4200, 2.4 GHz (4 CPUs), RAM 4G, and operating environment is win10 (64 bits), and development environment is VC++ (2015).

Performance evaluation is performed with the PSNR value and processing time of the denoised image by applying different denoising methods after adding random impulse noise between 0 and 255 and Gaussian noise with mean zero and variance 20 to the image with a ratio of 1:1 at the range of 10%-50%.

Fig. 2 shows the PSNR values obtained with varying noise density in a graphical form. Here, the horizontal axis represents the noise density and the vertical axis represents the mean value of the PSNR. The denoising methods used for the comparative evaluation are ROAD_TGM_HT, AVMF+WMF, SVM+AF, RAFF, and RAFF. Fig. 3 shows the noise detection rate in a graphical form when the noise density is changed. Here, the horizontal axis represents the noise density and the vertical axis represents the noise detection rate. The noise detection methods used for comparative evaluation are ROAD_TGM and MMV. Fig. 4 shows the noise images and the corresponding noise maps when the noise density changes, and the noise maps detected by the individual noise detection methods. We also show the denoised images with the individual denoising methods. Fig. 5 shows the time taken to detect noise using the individual methods in a graphical form when the noise density changes. Here, the horizontal axis represents the noise density, and the vertical axis represents the detection time in milliseconds. It can be seen that the noise detection time of our method is three times faster than other methods.

Fig. 2. Comparison of PSNR at different noise density

Fig 3. Comparison of noise detection rates at different noise density

Fig 4. (aa-ae) image corrupted with 10%,20%,30%,40%,50% noise, (ba-be) noise map, (ca-ce) noise map detected by ROAD_TGM, (da-de) noise map detected by MMV, (ea-ee) noise map detected by the proposed method, (fa-fe) denoised image by ROAD_TGM_HT, (ga-ge) denoised image by AVMF+WMF, (ha-he) denoised image by SVM+AF, (ia-ie) denoised image by RAFF, (ja-je) denoised image by proposed method.

Fig 5. Comparison of the time of noise detection with noise density.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a new denoising method using connectivity judgment and adaptive filter to improve the accuracy of noise detection and detection speed in the presence of mixed noise of different intensities and to improve the accuracy of noise reduction. To test the effectiveness of the proposed method, we measured the PSNR after noise removal using different denoising methods on image data with Gaussian noise and random impulse noise at the range of 10% to 50%. The experimental results show that the proposed denoising method is superior to the previous methods in terms of noise detection accuracy, speed and denoising. Future work will focus on improving the accuracy of noise detection and noise reduction in complex background environments. In the case of complex background environments, it seems reasonable to proceed by combining optimization methods.

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